

Prompt Gamma Absolute Efficiency Calibration of HPGe for Measurements of Activated Water at KATANA, JSI

Domen Govekar^{1,2,*}, Julijan Peric^{1,2}, Domen Kotnik¹, Vladimir Radulović^{1,2}

¹Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, Ljubljana, Slovenia;

²Faculty for Mathematics and Physics, University of Ljubljana, Jadranska cesta 19, Ljubljana, Slovenia

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803837

ABSTRACT

Accurate absolute efficiency calibration is essential for quantitative γ -ray spectroscopy in industry and in fusion and fission research. This work presents a geometry-consistent workflow for high-purity germanium detectors in which all measurements are performed on-axis. Below 2 MeV, the absolute scale is anchored with certified ^{152}Eu , ^{133}Ba , and ^{137}Cs sources. To extend coverage, neutron-induced prompt γ rays from Fe and KCl targets are recorded in a moderated field using an 8 cm water layer, with the detector held at the same 51.3 cm geometry. The analysis comprises energy calibration, peak fitting, decay and live-time corrections, and computation of full-energy peak efficiency. A single fit with a sixth-order polynomial applied to $\ln \varepsilon$ provides a continuous, monotonic efficiency curve from 30 keV to 7.6 MeV without high-energy extrapolation. The approach is traceable, reproducible, and readily re-validated after hardware or geometry changes, enabling routine analyses that span the sub-2 MeV region into the multi-MeV domain while maintaining a single, geometry-consistent calibration. The method is applicable to active γ detectors and is not limited to high-purity germanium.

Keywords: Absolute efficiency, HPGe, Prompt gamma, Gamma-ray spectroscopy

1. INTRODUCTION

High-purity germanium (HPGe) detectors are the workhorse of precise γ -ray spectroscopy in safeguards, nuclear data, environmental monitoring, and applied research. Their excellent energy resolution enables confident peak identification and quantification, provided the detector response is carefully calibrated. In practice, this means establishing an absolute efficiency curve that links fitted peak areas to emission rates across the energy range of interest.

Below about 2 MeV, the calibration task is well served by certified sources such as ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs , and ^{152}Eu . These provide numerous well-known lines that anchor the low- and mid-energy region with traceability to standard reference materials and tabulated emission probabilities [1]. Above 2 MeV, suitable standards become sparse and straight extrapolation of the curve becomes risky. To bridge this gap, neutron-induced prompt γ rays at well-established energies and relative intensities offer a practical way to extend the efficiency curve into the multi-MeV range [2].

This paper presents a compact workflow that can be adopted for routine use. The idea is simple: measure the certified sources and the prompt-capture targets at the same geometry, then fit a single smooth function to all data. The presentation is general for HPGe detectors, while figures and numbers are taken from the OF84 HPGe detector as a concrete example. All measurements were performed on-axis at a fixed distance of 51.3 cm so that the combined curve is geometry-consistent from the outset. A sixth-order polynomial in $\ln E$ fitted to $\ln \varepsilon$ provides a flexible but stable description from ~ 30 keV to ~ 7.6 MeV—adequate for routine analyses without resorting to ad-hoc high-energy extrapolations [1, 3].

*domen.govekar@ijs.si

Beyond the laboratory context, the resulting curve enables quantitative measurement of the ^{16}N high-energy lines (6.13 and 7.12 MeV) in the KATANA water-activation loop at the Jožef Stefan Institute [4, 5]. Because the calibration remains valid into the multi-MeV range, fitted peak areas can be converted to activities for operational diagnostics and transient and steady-state studies.

2. ENERGY AND RESOLUTION CALIBRATION

Energy calibration sets peak locations; resolution calibration sets integration width and separation from background. Tying regions of interest to the energy-dependent resolution keeps background treatment consistent. The fixed on-axis geometry removes view-factor and alignment confounders, so remaining effects trace to the detector–electronics chain. Together, these form a stable, reproducible foundation for the efficiency calibration.

2.1. Measurement setup

A coaxial, electrically cooled p-type HPGe detector labeled OF84 was coupled to a digital spectrometer (ORTEC DSPEC-502A) [6]. Bias, shaping, and acquisition settings were held constant throughout. The source or target was positioned on the detector axis at a fixed distance (51.3 cm) from end-cap to source, and alignment to within a few millimeters was verified. The overall geometry and positioning fixtures are shown schematically in Fig. 1.

Calibration sources ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs , and ^{152}Eu standards were used. Live-time fractions of $\geq 99\%$ were maintained, and background was treated by sideband modeling during peak fitting.

For prompt- γ measurements, a moderated neutron source was used to irradiate Fe and KCl targets; the HPGe was kept on-axis at the same distance as the calibration sources and using the same mount.

Figure 1. On-axis laboratory layout used for all measurements (not to scale). A: HPGe detector end-cap and axis (OF84). B: source/target holder position on axis. C: Moderator (water). D: Am-Be Neutron Source. E: Lead blocks. F: Paraffin wax blocks.

2.2. Energy and resolution calibration with standard sources

Certified sources at a fixed on-axis distance provided the basis for determining the energy and resolution calibration. Spectra were acquired under identical electronics settings, and a uniform peak-fitting procedure (Gaussian core with local sideband background and consistent regions of interest) was applied to all datasets [1, 3]. A set of well-separated lines spanning ≈ 80 keV to 1.4 MeV provided coverage

for both calibrations. The energies and fitted centroid channel numbers used in the calibration are listed in Table I.

Table I. Lines used for energy and resolution calibration. Residual is defined as $E_{tab} - E(ch)$ using the adopted calibration.

Element	Ch _{centroid}	E_γ [keV]	Residual [keV]	FWHM [keV]	σ_{FWHM} [keV]
¹⁵² Eu	258	121.8	-0.0445	1.23	0.00
¹⁵² Eu	517	244.7	0.0539	1.32	0.00
¹³³ Ba	584	276.4	0.0309	1.24	0.02
¹³³ Ba	640	302.9	0.0056	1.35	0.01
¹⁵² Eu	727	344.3	0.0910	1.38	0.00
¹³³ Ba	752	356.0	-0.0030	1.39	0.00
¹⁵² Eu	776	367.8	0.1202	1.41	0.02
¹³³ Ba	810	383.8	0.0163	1.42	0.01
¹⁵² Eu	868	411.1	0.0631	1.33	0.02
¹⁵² Eu	937	444.0	0.1320	1.47	0.01
¹⁵² Eu	1190	564.0	0.3016	1.71	0.05
¹³⁷ Cs	1396	661.7	0.1958	1.60	0.01
¹⁵² Eu	1432	678.6	0.2153	1.57	0.05
¹⁵² Eu	1453	688.7	0.2244	1.68	0.03
¹⁵² Eu	1644	778.9	0.1400	1.66	0.00
¹⁵² Eu	1831	867.4	-0.0294	1.71	0.01
¹⁵² Eu	2036	964.1	-0.1790	1.80	0.00
¹⁵² Eu	2123	1005.3	-0.1686	1.73	0.04
¹⁵² Eu	2293	1085.9	-0.2019	1.85	0.01
¹⁵² Eu	2301	1089.7	-0.2283	1.82	0.02
¹⁵² Eu	2342	1109.2	-0.4187	1.87	0.00
¹⁵² Eu	2348	1112.1	-0.2308	1.87	0.00
¹⁵² Eu	2561	1212.9	-0.1878	1.91	0.03
¹⁵² Eu	2743	1299.1	-0.2057	1.98	0.02
¹⁵² Eu	2973	1408.0	-0.2423	1.93	0.01
⁵⁶ Fe	12 704	6018.5	-1.4928	3.64	0.08
⁵⁶ Fe	16 109	7631.1	-2.2778	4.39	0.27
⁵⁶ Fe	16 139	7645.6	-2.2504	4.39	0.27

Energy calibration. Peak centroids from the selected lines were used to map channel to energy. A linear model was adopted over the working range,

$$E[\text{keV}] = a_0 + a_1 \text{Ch} \quad (1)$$

where the fitted coefficients a_0 and a_1 must be reported from the regression. The resulting relation is shown in Fig. 2. The calibration model order was selected as the lowest-order polynomial that leaves no systematic trend in the residuals (Table I). If significant curvature is observed at high channels in a specific acquisition configuration, a quadratic term can be introduced.

Resolution calibration. Full width at half maximum (FWHM) values were extracted for the same lines to characterize resolution versus energy. As expected for a stable HPGe system, the FWHM increased

Figure 2. Relation between channel number and energy for the OF84 HPGe detector. Centroid channel numbers used in the fit are listed in Table I.

slowly with energy, providing a reference curve for routine performance checks and for validating that subsequent efficiency measurements were taken under consistent conditions. The trend derived from the standard sources is plotted in Fig. 3 and is described by

$$\text{FWHM}(E) = \sqrt{1.25 + 0.00196 Ch}, \quad \text{Ch is channel number.} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3. Energy-dependent resolution (FWHM) derived from calibration lines. The corresponding centroid channel numbers for each point are listed in Table I.

3. EFFICIENCY CALIBRATION

While energy and resolution ensure correct peak placement and separation, the efficiency calibration links fitted peak areas to emission rates with traceability. For a line at energy E_γ with background-subtracted net counts N_p and live time t_{live} , the absolute full-energy peak efficiency is

$$\varepsilon(E_\gamma) = \frac{N_p}{A_{\text{ref}} e^{-\lambda \Delta t} P_\gamma(E_\gamma) t_{\text{live}}}, \quad (3)$$

where A_{ref} is the certificate activity at the reference date, λ the decay constant, Δt the elapsed time until start of calibration, and P_γ the emission probability [3]. Activities and emission probabilities were taken from the corresponding NIST SRM certificates [7].

On the solid-angle term. The efficiency $\varepsilon(E_\gamma)$ in Eq. (3) is defined as the *absolute full-energy peak efficiency for the fixed measurement geometry* (source/target on-axis at 51.3 cm). In this definition the geometric factor ($\Omega/4\pi$) is not written separately because it is inherently included in the measured efficiency: $\varepsilon(E) = \varepsilon_{\text{int}}(E) (\Omega/4\pi) T(E)$, where ε_{int} is the intrinsic detector response and $T(E)$ accounts for attenuation in the end-cap, air, and holders. Since all measurements were performed at the same on-axis distance and alignment, the geometric term is constant across datasets; separating it would convert the result to an intrinsic efficiency rather than the geometry-specific absolute efficiency used for routine activity determination in the KATANA geometry.

3.1. Standard-source anchors (sub-2 MeV)

Sealed ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs , and ^{152}Eu standards were measured on-axis under identical acquisition settings. Uniform regions of interest and sideband backgrounds were applied across runs, activities were decay-corrected to counting start, and tabulated P_γ values were used. These measurements populate the sub-2 MeV range with traceable points that set the absolute efficiency scale.

3.2. Prompt- γ extension and global fit (to ~ 7.6 MeV)

To extend coverage, prompt γ lines from Fe and KCl targets were recorded in a moderated neutron field using an 8 cm water moderator; the HPGe was kept on-axis at the same distance from the target as for the calibration sources (measurement setup is shown in Fig. 4). Prompt lines provide accurate energies and reliable *relative* intensities at multi-MeV energies [2]. Because the neutron field and target capture rate are not known absolutely, these data were treated as relative and merged with the standard-source anchors through their overlap (~ 0.7 – 1.5 MeV), which fixes the absolute scale.

Figure 4. Schematic set-up for prompt- γ measurements (neutron field moderated by 8 cm water; Fe and KCl targets; HPGe held on-axis at 51.3 cm).

Prompt- γ counting model and relative scaling. For a prompt line i observed in prompt- γ dataset j , the net peak area n_{ij} can be written as

$$n_{ij} = K_j I_{\gamma,i} \varepsilon(E_{ij}) t_{\text{live},j}, \quad (4)$$

where $I_{\gamma,i}$ is the recommended prompt- γ relative intensity for the given target (Fe or Cl), $\varepsilon(E_{ij})$ is the full-energy peak efficiency at energy E_{ij} , and K_j is an unknown dataset-dependent proportionality constant that absorbs the (unknown) neutron field strength, capture rate in the target, target mass/thickness effects, and any constant attenuation factors specific to dataset j . Rearranging gives a relative efficiency estimate

$$\varepsilon(E_{ij}) \propto \frac{n_{ij}}{I_{\gamma,i} t_{\text{live},j}}, \quad (5)$$

with the missing absolute scale contained in K_j .

The relative prompt- γ points are therefore combined with the standard-source anchors through a joint fit in log-space, where each prompt- γ dataset is allowed a free normalization while sharing a single global energy dependence.

A single sixth-order polynomial in $\ln E$ was fitted to $\ln \varepsilon$ over the entire span,

$$\ln \varepsilon(E) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln E + \beta_2 (\ln E)^2 + \beta_3 (\ln E)^3 + \beta_4 (\ln E)^4 + \beta_5 (\ln E)^5 + \beta_6 (\ln E)^6, \quad E \text{ in keV}, \quad (6)$$

a flexible yet stable form for the low-energy rise and gradual high-energy fall typical of coaxial HPGe at moderate distances. All lines (standard-source and prompt- γ) were fitted jointly with per-dataset offsets for the relative (prompt- γ) sets:

$$y_{ij} = \sum_{k=0}^6 \beta_k (\ln E_{ij})^k + \delta_j + \epsilon_{ij}, \quad y_{ij} \equiv \ln(n_{ij}/\kappa_{ij}), \quad \delta_j = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{(calibration sources)} \\ \text{free} & \text{(prompt-}\gamma\text{)} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

with weights $w_{ij} = 1/\sigma_{y,ij}^2$. The global parameters follow from

$$(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\delta}) = \arg \min_{\beta, \delta} \sum_{j,i} w_{ij} \left[y_{ij} - \sum_{k=0}^6 \beta_k (\ln E_{ij})^k - \delta_j \right]^2, \quad (8)$$

and the estimated absolute efficiency is

$$\hat{\varepsilon}(E) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=0}^6 \hat{\beta}_k (\ln E)^k \right). \quad (9)$$

Here n_{ij} is the net peak area, κ_{ij} the known multiplicative factor (live time, decay, emission probability, and any geometry/summing corrections applied consistently), E_{ij} the line energy, and ϵ_{ij} the residual. The indices j and i represent the dataset (an individual spectrum/measurement run) and the identified γ -ray line (peak) within dataset j , respectively.

For the OF84 dataset at fixed distance, the fitted curve tracks the standard-source points below 2 MeV and the prompt- γ points up to ~ 7.6 MeV, with residuals showing no systematic trend (Fig. 5). Coefficients for the polynomial are given in Table II.

Figure 5. Absolute efficiency points (markers) and single sixth-order global fit (line) for HPGe (OF84), combining standard-source anchors with prompt- γ lines.

Table II. Sixth-order log–log efficiency fit coefficients for HPGe (OF84, 51.3 cm).

Coefficient	Value
β_0	−85.016
β_1	40.3803
β_2	−5.240 73
β_3	−0.574 05
β_4	0.199 567
β_5	−0.017 308 0
β_6	0.000 501 5

4. CONCLUSION

Calibrating at a single, on-axis geometry for both certified sources and prompt-capture measurements, and fitting one sixth-order $\ln \varepsilon - \ln E$ polynomial to all points, yields a compact, monotonic absolute-efficiency curve from roughly 30 keV to 7.6 MeV for HPGe. Using Fe and Cl prompt lines to extend coverage provides well-defined anchors at high energy and removes the need for uncertain extrapolations beyond the source region.

The workflow is intentionally simple: identical acquisition settings, uniform peak fitting, and consistent geometry across all datasets. In practice, this makes the calibration easy to maintain and to re-validate after hardware service or configuration changes. Because all data share the same geometry, any drift can be traced and corrected without reworking the entire analysis chain.

The approach is general for coaxial HPGe detectors at moderate distance. To increase line density above 2 MeV, one or two capture targets matched to the required energies and count-rate limits can be selected

(e.g., Mn, Ni; Gd if very high yield is needed). Longer measuring times or a higher-intensity neutron field can reduce scatter and tighten the global fit. Rate effects and resolution stability should be checked at higher rates. Geometry and attenuation in holders, moderator, and shielding should be modeled so that precision gains are not lost to transport bias.

Overall, the method delivers a traceable, reproducible efficiency calibration that supports day-to-day spectroscopy as well as higher-energy applications within the same, geometry-consistent framework.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the support of the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (project codes P2-0405 Fusion technologies; P2-0073 Reactor physics; PR-09769/PR12326/PR-12842 Training of young researchers, NC-0022 Water activation in nuclear reactors).

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Gilmore. *Practical Gamma-Ray Spectrometry*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ, 3 edition (2024).
- [2] H. Choi, R. Firestone, R. Lindstrom, G. Molnár, S. Mughabghab, R. Paviotti-Corcuera, Z. Révay, A. Trkov, and C. Zhou. "Database of Prompt Gamma Rays from Slow Neutron Capture for Elemental Analysis." Technical Reports Series IAEA-TECDOC-1263, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna (2006). Final report of a coordinated research project.
- [3] G. F. Knoll. *Radiation Detection and Measurement*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ, 4 edition (2010).
- [4] D. Kotnik, J. Peric, D. Govekar, L. Snoj, and I. Lengar. "KATANA - water activation facility at JSI TRIGA, Part I: Final design and activity calculations." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, volume 57(3), p. 103233 (2025). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1738573324004820>.
- [5] D. Kotnik, J. Peric, D. Govekar, L. Snoj, and I. Lengar. "KATANA - water activation facility at JSI TRIGA, Part II: First experiments." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, volume 57(4), p. 103290 (2025). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1738573324005400>.
- [6] Mirion Technologies (ORTEC), Oak Ridge, TN. *DSPEC 50/502A Digital Spectrometer Hardware Manual* (2021). URL <https://www.ortec-online.com/>.
- [7] A. Kramida, Y. Ralchenko, J. Reader, and N. A. Team. "NIST Atomic Spectra Database (ASD) — Lines Form." (2024). URL https://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/ASD/lines_form.html. Online database.